

Finite element investigation of the biaxial tests of the SCSC-Plate as the deck plate of a trough bridge

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ABSTRACT

For the SCSC (Steel-Concrete-Steel-Composite) Plate (1) as a trough bridge deck plate, the urgent question is which mechanisms are responsible for its load-bearing capacity. Previous research has shown that the shear force transfer between the deck plate and the bottom plate in the case of a slab bridge can be described by a truss model in the concrete core (2). In the case of a trough bridge, the slab is subjected to significant tensile forces in the longitudinal direction of the bridge, which causes cracks in the concrete and calls into question the load-bearing capacity in the transverse direction.

Biaxial tests are carried out on this topic at the Technische Universität Wien Institute of Structural Engineering - Research Unit Steel Structures. The results of these experiments are supported by finite element analysis. The main objective of this work is to investigate how these shear forces behave under the tension from the main load-bearing behaviour and what happens to the test specimen under this biaxial force action.

In this study, the focus is on the finite element modelling of three different specimens and the comparison of the computational results with the experimental results.

The experiments are modelled using the Explicit module of Dassault Systèmes' ABAQUS finite element software (ABAQUS/CAE 2024).

The main modelling inputs, techniques, and results for each specimen at different loading levels are presented. The effects of the tensile forces on the shear capacity of the SCSC-Plate are analysed in detail.

Keywords: SCSC-Plate, shear connectors, finite element analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

The SCSC plate is assembled as follows: Perfobond shear connectors are welded onto two metal plates. The two resulting construction elements (bottom plate with shear connector and top plate with shear connector) are folded together and then filled with concrete. After the concrete has hardened, the shear connections are activated by the concrete. In this way, the top and bottom plates are joined with a shear-resistant connection. The shear connectors have a spacing of 440 mm in the slab bridge and 500 mm in the trough bridge. This connection type requires more detailed investigation by experiment and FE analysis.

The bottom region of a trough bridge, where the SCSC-Plate is positioned, functions as a tension member. The SCSC-Plate is most exposed to tensile forces in the centre of the structure, as shown in *Fig. 1*. Because the concrete lies in the plate, it is cracked by the tensile forces. The challenge is to ensure that the concrete can withstand the shear and compression forces perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the bridge under these circumstances. This investigation aims to verify the

ability of current modelling techniques and material models' ability to analyse the test specimens' structural behaviour. Verifying these models allows for verifying other parts of the bridge or even the complete bridge models without experimental tests. Finite element modelling also played a central role in developing and optimising the biaxial tests. Parallel FE analyses were used to identify and eliminate several weaknesses in the test setup.

Fig. 1. Critical area and overview of the trough bridge

Fig. 2 shows the concept of the biaxial tests. The test specimens represent a part of the SCSC-Plate. The tests were carried out in two steps. In the first step, the tensile forces from the Ultimate Limit State (1 ULS-LM71) were applied (shown with blue arrows). In the second step, the shear load was applied (indicated by red arrows) with one load cycle (up to 1 ULS shear load, $F_{\text{shear, ULS}} = 476 \text{ kN}$ as determined by Egly (3)) and then until failure of the specimen. Both tension and shear were applied with force control.

Fig. 2. Development of the test concept; a) critical area of the trough bridge; b) biaxial test specimen; c) cross-section of the SCSC-Plate; d) biaxial test setup

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

2.1 Experimental specimen details

Four types of biaxial test specimens with different shear connectors were planned; more detailed information can be found in Spreitzer-Gröbner (4). This paper covers the first type and its three variants, as shown in *Fig. 3*.

The test specimen 1/1 (TS 1/1) is used to analyse the conditions in the SCSC-Plate without reinforcement for comparison purposes.

Test specimen 1/2 (TS 1/2) is the extension of TS 1/1 with additional elongations (0.8 mm/m) from the trough bridge application.

Test specimen 1/3 is test specimen 1/2 with additional continuous main reinforcements and transverse reinforcing bars on top. There are $D = 20$ mm diameter main rebars in all concrete dowels and six $D = 10$ mm diameter transverse rebars in each concrete core, spaced equidistantly.

Fig. 3 Three variants of the test specimen 1

The tests were focused on one shear connector element, which is in the middle and welded to the top plate. The bottom plate is separated under the middle shear connector so that the elongation from the trough bridge main load can be adjusted as wished. On the edges, the shear connectors were welded to the base plates and strengthened to cause the specimens to fail in the tested concrete areas. One was the concrete core with different construction variants (with or without reinforcement in the concrete core), and the other was the local environment of the shear connectors, as shown in *Fig. 4*.

Fig. 4 Expected failure regions: 1. area of the shear connector, 2. concrete core

2.2 Material constitutive models

Simulia ABAQUS 2024 Explicit offers two concrete material constitutive models, the brittle cracking model and the concrete damaged plasticity model (CDP) (5). The brittle cracking model is optimal for problems with dominant tensile cracking but cannot describe plastic behaviour in compression. Biaxial problems are assumed to have both dominant crack widths and dominant concrete crushing at the shear connectors. Several previous studies have shown (1, 2) that the CDP model – developed by Lee and Fenves (6) from the model of Lubliner et al. (7) - performs well in the case of composite structures. These studies have investigated the SCSC-Plate as part of a slab bridge, where the concrete dowels are not under substantial tension forces and are not cracked. The concrete material model must also correctly describe load cycles and multi-step multidirectional loading conditions. Tensile and compressive damage parameters that reduce the stiffness of damaged concrete under cyclic loading are included in the CDP model. The model's reaction to a load cycle can be seen in *Fig. 5a*.

The concrete was self-compacting concrete (SCC) with a mean compressive strength (f_{cm}) of 58.44 MPa, while the tensile strength (f_{ctm}) was 4.1 MPa. The modulus of elasticity, Poisson's ratio and density were 32.3 GPa, 0.2 and 2400 kg/m³ respectively. Compressive strength was determined by cube tests, while the other properties were based on the recommendations of the CEB-FIP Model Code 2010 (8) and Carrasquillo et al. (9). In determining the concrete parameters, time-dependent factors such as curing time, ageing and storage temperature were considered.

The model developed by Popovics (10) and applied by Yip (11) was adopted for the compressive behaviour.

The concrete behaviour under tensile stresses is specified using the stress-crack displacement definition based on the fracture energy criterion according to CEB-FIP Model Code 1990 (12). Exponential tensile softening law has been considered. The fracture energy was calculated taking into account the maximum aggregate size $d_{max} = 8$ mm.

The reinforcement (B550B) and the structural steel (S355) had a linear elastic-linear hardening constitutive model according to ÖNORM EN 1993-1-14 (13), see *Fig. 5b*.

Fig. 5. a) Uniaxial load cycle of CDP model (5); b) quad-linear material model with strain hardening (13)

2.3 Description of FE models

Concrete, the structural steel, and the main reinforcements are solid element types C3D8R or C3D8. The element type C3D8R (8-node linear brick, reduced integration) was used where applicable to reduce the calculation time. C3D8 (linear 8-node brick) was required where concentrated forces are transmitted to minimise the "hourglass" effect, for example, at the concrete dowels' location.

The geometric conditions required elements with tiny dimensions, drastically affecting the computation time. The shortest element edge is found in the main reinforcement and is approximately 0.8 mm. The maximum number of elements is over 3.1 million.

For the reasons mentioned above, the transverse bars with a diameter of 10 mm are not configured as solid bars but instead as B31 beams (2-node linear beams in space).

Mass scaling factor 10 was used for the whole models to speed up the analysis without artificially increasing the loading rate. The load rate is chosen to complete the computation faster, and the rules of quasi-static states are not violated ($T_{\text{Step-tension}} = 0.25$ s, $T_{\text{Step-shear}} = 0.527$ s).

The contact between the main reinforcement and the concrete is a tie constraint. The transverse bars are embedded in the concrete with the embedded region constraint. Penalty contact algorithms between concrete and steel are specified with a coefficient of friction of 0.3 and between steel and steel 0.2.

The analyses are force-controlled to reproduce the load cycles generated during the experiments. This means the specimens are accelerated after failure, and the kinetic energy curve increases rapidly, as shown by the blue curves in *Fig. 6-8*.

3 VERIFICATION OF THE FE SIMULATION WITH ENERGY QUANTITIES

A few principles must be considered to achieve good-quality numerical analysis results with ABAQUS software. Because this problem is analysed with the dynamic explicit module, the quasi-static state must be realised until failure. The amount of kinetic energy (ALLKE) should be minimal compared to other physically significant amounts of energy (e.g. internal energy ALLIE).

Furthermore, it is essential that the energy balance (ETOTAL) is observed, i.e. it remains constant. This constant must be zero because the system has no initial kinetic energy ($ETOTAL \approx 0$).

Another limitation is to keep the artificial strain energy close to zero ($ALLAE \approx 0$).

SIMULIA also recommends that the work done by contact penalties remains very low ($ALLPW \approx 0$).

Fig. 6-8 presents the energy-time and shear load-time curves, demonstrating that the FE results satisfy the abovementioned conditions.

Fig. 6. Shear load-time and Energy-Time curve TS 1/1

Fig. 7. Shear load-time and Energy-Time curve TS 1/2

Fig. 8. Shear load-time and Energy-Time curve TS 1/3

4 COMPARISON OF FINITE ELEMENT AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Comparison of Experimental and Load-Displacement Responses

The numerical results of the TS1/1 (without tension force) are satisfying, as shown in *Fig. 9-11* and *Table 1*. The test specimens under dominant tension forces (TS 1/2 and TS 1/3) with FE analysis show higher stiffness at the unloading branch than the experiments. The numerical model behaves much more stiffly than the experiments at the beginning. One reason for this is that the FE analysis describes idealised conditions and does not consider imperfections such as manufacturing inaccuracies, material inhomogeneities and boundary condition imperfections.

After reloading and some concrete damage, the ascending branch of the FEM shows a much less stiff behaviour than before, which the experiments already represent more accurately.

It is, therefore, essential that each specimen can withstand the multiple ULS loads, both experimentally and numerically. *Table 2* compares the corresponding shear load capacities.

From the shear load-time curve of TS 1/3 in *Fig. 8* (at 0.5 s) and the shear load-displacement curve in *Fig. 11* (at 1 mm), the curve falls back, the first concrete dowel fails at this point, and the force measured on the support falls. After a certain amount of shear deformation and force redistribution, the system calms down, and the first concrete dowel takes up the forces again, but not as much as before. These numerical instabilities are not present in the experiments.

Fig 9. Comparison of shear load-displacement curves TS 1/1

Fig 10. Comparison of shear load-displacement curves TS 1/2

Fig 11. Comparison of shear load-displacement curves TS 1/3

Table 1. Comparison of the stiffness C at the reloading branch [kN/mm]

	TS 1/1	TS 1/2	TS 1/3
Experiment	1107	691	997
Numerical	1219	1571	1878
Relation C_{Exp} / C_{Num}	1.10	2.27	1.92

Table 2. Comparison of the shear capacity F_{shear} of the specimens [kN]

	TS 1/1	TS 1/2	TS 1/3
Experiment	2175	1650	2400
Numerical	1700	2100	1700
Relation $F_{shear, Exp} / F_{shear, Num}$	1.28	0.78	1.41

In Fig. 12 left, the crack pattern can be seen according to ABAQUS and according to the experiment for specimen 1/3. Experiments show smaller angles between cracks and shear connectors. The deformations of the reinforcement after failure are very similar by experiment and numerical method, as shown in Fig. 12 right.

Figure 12. Opened specimen TS 1/3 after failure with ABAQUS results; left: crack pattern; right: deformation

5 CONCLUSIONS

Even though ABAQUS energy curves say that the results are valid, it can be assumed that this is not entirely the case. The results of the specimen without tension step are good. The stiffness of the specimens with numerical results is not satisfying. A reason for the excessive shear stiffness in test specimens with tensile loading is the irreversible plastic deformation in the cracks. Fig. 13 visualises how far the cracks plastify at the end of the tensile step in the concrete core. The CDP model does not allow these cracks to close during the shear phase, and the cracks remain filled with

material. It gives a certain rigidity to the system, which would probably not be present with such crack widths. The cracks in TS 1/3 are better distributed by the reinforcement, which is why the concrete model is more suitable in this case.

CDP gives good results for regular crack openings (in this paper these are much larger, 2 mm), so it would be reasonable to model the cracks with shear friction properties and use discrete gaps.

Further modelling options include bond slip contact between the main reinforcement and the concrete. This behaviour also has a reducing effect on the shear stiffness.

Fig. 13. Plastic strain and crack pattern at the end of tensile phase; left: TS 1/2; right: TS 1/3

In conclusion, modelling with these inputs is useful for the slab bridge models, but further investigation is required in the case of the trough bridge.

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